

ANALYSIS OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION POLICY AND NEW PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES

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Abstract. *The article discusses the mechanisms of promoting the system of inclusive education in our country and the problems of mastering the professional competence of teachers in this field. The features of working with children with special needs in the system of inclusive education on the example of foreign countries are also highlighted.*

Keywords: *inclusive education, students with disabilities, politics, the Russian education system, methods, research, organization.*

In recent years, the social role of education has increased, and the attitude towards all types of education has changed in most countries of the world. Education is considered as the leading factor of social and economic development. The reason for such attention is that the most important value and main capital of modern society is a person who is able to search for new knowledge, acquire it and make non-standard decisions. Therefore, education plays a decisive role in the development of individuals and society. World civilization shows that progress in other fields cannot be achieved without raising the education system to a higher level.

Article 4 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" states that non-discrimination in the field of education and provision of equal opportunities for education are the main principles in the field of education. Article 9 states that "Children with physical, mental, sensorial or mental disabilities, as well as children who need long-term treatment, are placed in state specialized educational institutions, general secondary and secondary special education. receives education in an inclusive form in organizations or individually at home." it has been shown.

At the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly in September 2017, the draft of the International Convention "On the Rights of Youth" was developed. "The rights of young people are, first of all, their right to a peaceful and healthy life and education. ...Ensuring that our growing young generation matures and receives high-quality and excellent education is always a priority for us."

In the countries of the world, special attention is paid to raising children with disabilities and in need of social protection, helping them to take their rightful place in society. The United Nations "Universal Declaration of Human Rights", "Declaration on the Rights of the Mentally Retarded", "Convention on the Rights of the Disabled", "Education for All" plan is correct. Dakar Declaration, "Asia and Oceania Program of Measures for the Protection of the Rights of Persons with Disabilities", "Standard Provisions on Ensuring Equal Opportunities for Persons with Disabilities", "Convention on the Rights of the Child" and other international agreements The main goal of the regulations is aimed at protecting children with disabilities, and these international legal frameworks provide for the effective introduction of an inclusive approach to the educational process.

Effective scientific, scientific-technical, scientific-pedagogical researches are being carried out on the world scale, taking into account the mental state of children who need special attention, methods of psychological correction, formation of humane relations in families, communities and groups, increasing the capabilities of technological aids. Pedagogical-psychological aspects of inclusive education in the general education system, meeting the educational needs of children with disabilities, creating conditions for their legal equality, problems related to strengthening their position as a member of society form the basis of these researches. Taking into account the individual characteristics and adaptive capabilities of children, technological provision of their social adaptation and support occupy a special place in the improvement of the pedagogical system of organizing the educational process.

The concept of inclusive education is based on the idea of an "inclusive society", where everyone prefers to include others (persons of different race, religion, culture, disability) for active and equal participation in social life, everyone's corresponds to their interests, increases their ability to live independently, and ensures the equality of their rights.

Professor Peter Mittler of the University of Manchester writes: "Inclusive education is a step towards the ultimate goal of achieving the ultimate goal of inclusive education for all children and adults, regardless of gender, age, ethnicity, ability, disability or not." creating a community. to participate in society and contribute to it" .

The international experience of inclusive education already has a long history. In recent years, foreign authors have published many books and many studies devoted to the analysis of inclusive education processes and its impact.

European countries have formed the definition and understanding of inclusive education, created a regulatory framework for education in public schools with special conditions for children with disabilities. The educational policy of Russia focuses on inclusion as a principle of changing social relations in education. Today, in modern conditions, it is clear that there is a need to change the model of special education. In this new model, the interaction of special and general educational institutions remains relevant for more effective organization.

Providing resources for the inclusive process is an important systemic element of organizational and meaningful changes in general education. The Russian experience of inclusive practice is associated with the long stage of the experimental and design regime of educational institutions, the author's adaptation of educational conditions for the needs of children with disabilities. Therefore, the question of professional assessment of the quality of the inclusion process and its effectiveness in relation to different categories of children is relevant.

In the conditions of top-down strategy of changes ("top-down decisions"), it is important to assess the readiness of this or that educational institution to implement an inclusive approach, and to correct mistakes. Now we understand that the school is going through two main stages - the stage of preparation for the strategy of inclusive development and the stage of implementation of changes in the management of the learning process, culture and practice.

Y.A. According to Gerasimenko, inclusive education is recognition of the value of children of different categories (special educational needs, different ethnic groups, belonging to a certain social group), their characteristics and learning abilities.

Regional models of development of inclusive education differ from each other in 5 main factors:

- 1) the position of educational institutions and the scientific community

- 2) development of psychological and pedagogical support services;
- 3) activities of public organizations;
- 4) availability of trained pedagogical personnel;
- 5) opportunities for financing educational services.

Russia's inclusive education experience has a rich history of design and experimental activities. Under the influence of mass media, the attitude of parents of ordinary children to joint education is gradually changing. To a greater extent, parents of children with disabilities expect special conditions and individual support from the educational institution and tend to see the main result and impact of inclusion in improving their child's ability to adapt. The civil status of adults is changing, and more and more parents understand the social importance of the problem of involving people with disabilities in society, but sometimes the general positive trends are rejected by one particular case. The position of mass media is very important for any social changes.

Against the background of the development of inclusive processes, the role of parents in their interaction with the school is changing. In general, the practice of inclusive education in Russia, despite existing regional differences, currently has a number of common limitations and problems. Inclusive education of disabled children is not regulated by regulatory legal documents, there is no mechanism for financing and implementation of special educational conditions for teaching such children in a public school. The most important task for the development of inclusive education is the training of managers of inclusive educational institutions, teachers and specialists who implement educational practices.

All state reforms related to the introduction of inclusive education in foreign countries and related to large-scale programs aimed at teaching (teachers, teachers of higher education institutions, the number of students, difficulties in teaching through professional development courses for teachers working with students who encounter them). This is a new principle of training teachers working in public schools. It is not related to the teacher's scientific knowledge, it is related to general pedagogical pro-confessional competencies and skills. In Russia, the department "psychology and pedagogy of special and inclusive education" was opened in the educational-methodological association of universities working according to this standard, the main task of which is to develop and review the main curricula, teachers and writing training manuals and textbooks for the training of inclusive education specialists.

In order to gain self-confidence and prevent disappointment in children who need special attention, the teacher's activities should be carried out in cooperation with parents. In inclusive education, teachers need to instill a sense of responsibility among all children in the classroom to improve the basic conditions necessary to ensure that basic teacher training and schooling work for all. Providing education according to the interests, knowledge and abilities of students who need special attention is a common activity in the classroom.

Inclusive education based on children with special needs is also beneficial to society. This, in turn, is the first step towards integration of a child with a physical or mental developmental disability in a regular kindergarten or school. In an integrated society, everyone has equal rights, it is a whole society. Through inclusive education, society becomes an integrated society and promotes effective pedagogic principles that benefit all children. It is considered normal that people are different, and based on the nature and stages of the learning process, the child should be adapted not to the requirements of this process, but to the needs of the child.

The goal of inclusive education implemented in general education schools is to enable children with special needs to study under the same conditions as their normal peers, to give them equal rights and equal opportunities, to interact with them in a friendly manner, and to facilitate their social adaptation to society. is to create necessary pedagogical-psychological and correctional conditions for students' education. If all ordinary children go to general education schools, children who need special attention should also be included. It is important that inclusive education is started from the family and preschool educational institutions. This will allow children to communicate with others, meet the demands of the social environment and, at the same time, acquire the skills to meet their daily and household needs early, adapt to life, and learn lessons in time along with their peers in general education schools, will help them acquire the skills of a responsible approach to tasks. Inclusive education in general education schools is an educational system that is flexible, individualized and provides equal rights and opportunities to all children, children with special needs or children with difficult upbringing due to other reasons, orphans. Also, inclusive education - treating all children equally, regardless of nationality, race, body color, social origin, material and spiritual status, family's position in society, physical or developmental disabilities, education is meant to support every possibility in them.

The process of inclusive education in comprehensive schools has its own complexities, and serious demands are placed on officials and teachers working in this field. In this type of education, the head of the class, subject teachers, tutors, masters of professional skills perform support services. The difference between healthy children and children who need special attention is not joining their peers due to their limited physical ability, shyness, shyness or humiliation, and some who are stubborn and capricious due to excessive care in the family. occurs.

Each inclusive education has a pedagogue with special training (resource). The importance of the prestige of inclusive education institutions depends on teachers who have this special training. Because he advises and helps the group tutor, provides special teaching equipment and supplies, conducts explanatory work with parents, teachers, and, if necessary, prepares the lesson schedule and program. makes changes, justifies them. It also increases the qualifications of teachers working in this direction, enriches knowledge, organizes health services, and creates a comfortable psychological environment. This educational activity program depends on a number of special, regional and level factors. They serve to prepare society's perspective, needs, resource requirements, and specialists.

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